

Face Recognition based Attendance Management System

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Abstract—In this digital era, face recognition system plays a vital role in almost every sector. Face recognition is one of the mostly used biometrics. It can be used for security, authentication, identification, and has got many more advantages. Despite of having low accuracy when compared to iris recognition and fingerprint recognition, it is being widely used due to its contactless and non-invasive process. Furthermore, face recognition system can also be used for attendance marking in schools, colleges, offices, etc. This system aims to build a class attendance system which uses the concept of face recognition as existing manual attendance system is time consuming and cumbersome to maintain. And there may be chances of proxy attendance. Thus, the need for this system increases. This system consists of four phases- database creation, face detection, face recognition, attendance updation. Database is created by the images of the students in class. Face detection and recognition is performed using Haar-Cascade classifier and Local Binary Pattern Histogram algorithm respectively. Faces are detected and recognized from live streaming video of the classroom. Attendance will be mailed to the respective faculty at the end of the session

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional method of attendance marking is a tedious task in many schools and colleges. It is also an extra burden to the faculties who should mark attendance by manually calling the names of students which might take about 5 minutes of entire session. This is time consuming. There are some chances of proxy attendance. Therefore, many institutes started deploying many other techniques for recording attendance like use of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) [3], iris recognition [4], fingerprint recognition, and so on. However, these systems are queue based which might consume more time and are intrusive in nature. Face recognition has set an important biometric feature, which can be easily acquirable and is non-intrusive. Face recognition based systems are relatively oblivious to various facial expressions. Face recognition system consists of two categories: verification and face identification. Face verification is an 1:1 matching process, it compares face image against the template face images and whereas is an 1:N problems that compares a query face images [1]. The purpose of this system is to build an attendance system which is based on face recognition techniques. Here face of an individual will be considered for marking attendance. Nowadays, face recognition is gaining more popularity and has been widely used. In this paper, we proposed a system which detects the

faces of students from live streaming video of classroom and attendance will be marked if the detected face is found in the database. This new system will consume less time than compared to traditional methods.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Traditional attendance tracking methods in educational institutions and workplaces often rely on manual processes, such as paper registers or card-based systems. These methods are time-consuming, prone to errors, and lack efficiency. The need for a more accurate, automated, and streamlined attendance system has become evident in the context of modern technology.

This research addresses the challenge of developing a reliable Smart Attendance System using OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision). The goal is to create an intelligent system that can automatically recognize and record attendance, eliminating the shortcomings of conventional methods. OpenCV, with its robust image processing capabilities, offers an opportunity to develop a system that can identify individuals in real-time through facial recognition.

The key issues to be tackled in this research include:

- 1) *Accuracy and Precision*: Achieving high accuracy in recognizing individuals to ensure precise attendance tracking.
- 2) *Real-time Recognition*: Designing the system to operate in real-time, allowing for efficient attendance recording without causing delays.
- 3) *Adaptability to Web Environment*: Developing a system that can adapt to different lighting conditions, camera angles, and variations in individual appearances.
- 4) *Privacy and Security*: Implementing measures to address privacy concerns and ensuring the security of the collected attendance data.
- 5) *User-Friendly Interface*: Creating an intuitive and user-friendly interface for both administrators and end-users to facilitate easy implementation and monitoring.

This research aims to contribute to the advancement of attendance tracking systems, making them more accurate, efficient, and adaptable to the needs of educational institutions and workplaces.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

Authors in [3] proposed a model of an automated attendance system. The model focuses on how face recognition incorporated with Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) detect the authorized students and counts as they get in and get out from the classroom. The system keeps the authentic record of every registered student. The system also keeps the data of every student registered for a particular course in the attendance log and provides necessary information according to the need. In this paper [4], authors have designed and implemented an attendance system which uses iris biometrics.

Initially, the attendees were asked to register their details along with their unique iris template. At the time of attendance, the system automatically took class attendance by capturing the eye image of each attendee, recognizing their iris, and searching for a match in the created database. The prototype was web based.

In [5], authors proposed an attendance system based on facial recognition. The algorithms like Viola-Jones and Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) features along with Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier were used to implement the system. Various real time scenarios such as scaling, illumination, occlusions and pose was considered by the authors. Quantitative analysis was done on the basis of Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) values and was implemented in MATLAB GUI.

Authors in [6] researches to get best facial recognition algorithm (Eigenface and Fisherface) provided by the Open CV 2.4.8 by comparing the Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve and then implemented it in the attendance system. Based on the experiments carried out in this paper, the ROC curve proved that, Eigenface achieves better result than Fisherface. System implemented using Eigenface algorithm achieved an accuracy rate of 7090

In [7], authors proposed a method for student attendance system in classroom using face recognition technique by combining Discrete Wavelet Transforms (DWT) and Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). These algorithms were used to extract the features of student's face followed by applying Radial Basis Function (RBF) for classifying the facial objects. This system achieved an accuracy rate of 82

IV. ARCHITECTURE

Typically this process can be divided into four stages,

A. Dataset Creation

Images of students are captured using a web cam. Multiple images of single student will be acquired with varied gestures and angles. These images undergo pre-processing. The images are cropped to obtain the Region of Interest (ROI) which will be further used in recognition process. Next step is to resize the cropped images to particular pixel position. Then these images will be converted from RGB to gray scale images. And then these images will be saved as the names of respective student in a folder.

Fig. 1. System Architecture

B. Face Detection

Face detection here is performed using Haar-Cascade Classifier with Open CV. Haar Cascade algorithm needs to be trained to detect human faces before it can be used for face detection. This is called feature extraction. The haar cascade training data used is an XML file haarcascade-frontal-facedefault. The haar features shown in Fig.2. will be used for feature extraction.

Fig. 2. Haar Features

C. Face Recognition

Face recognition process can be divided into three steps-prepare training data, train face recognizer, prediction. Here training data will be the images present in the dataset. They will be assigned with a integer label of the student it belongs

to. These images are then used for face recognition. Face recognizer used in this system is Local Binary Pattern Histogram. Initially, the list of local binary patterns (LBP) of entire face is obtained. These LBPs are converted into decimal number and then histograms of all those decimal values are made. At the end, one histogram will be formed for each images in the training data. Later, during recognition process histogram of the face to be recognized is calculated and then compared with the already computed histograms and returns the best matched label associated with the student it belongs to [9]

D. Attendance Updation

After face recognition process, the recognized faces will be marked as present in the excel sheet and the rest will be marked as absent and the list of absentees will be mailed to the respective faculties. Faculties will be updated with monthly attendance sheet at the end of every month.

V. ALGORITHMS

A smart attendance system implemented using Python can involve various algorithms depending on its specific requirements and components. Here are some common algorithms that might be used:

Fig. 3. Sample Image after detection

A. Face Detection and Recognition

1) *Face Detection*:: Face detection algorithms like Haar cascade classifier, HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradients), or deep learning-based methods like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) can be used to detect faces in images or video streams.

2) *Face Recognition*:: Face recognition algorithms such as Eigenfaces, Fisherfaces, LBPH (Local Binary Patterns Histograms), or deep learning-based approaches like Siamese networks or FaceNet can be employed to recognize faces and match them against known individuals in the database.

3) *Bounding Box Prediction*:: Multiple bounding boxes, each with a confidence score and class probabilities, are predicted by YOLO for each grid cell. To eliminate redundant or low-confidence data, non-maximum suppression is used boxes.

4) *Strengths*:: YOLO is known for its speed, making it suitable for applications like real-time object tracking, surveillance, and autonomous vehicles. It can detect multiple objects in a single pass.

5) *Limitations*:: YOLO may struggle with small or closely spaced objects, and its accuracy may not match some other models for certain tasks.

B. Faster CNN (Convolutional Neural Network)

1) *Overview*:: A popular object detection framework called Faster R-CNN builds on the success of the R-CNN family. In order to quickly create probable object regions inside an image, it offers a Region Proposal Network (RPN).

2) *Region Proposal Network (RPN)*:: The RPN generates region proposals (bounding box candidates) by sliding a small neural network over the image. These proposals are refined and classified as objects or background regions.

3) *Two-Step Process*:: Faster R-CNN follows a two-step process, where the first step generates region proposals using the RPN, and the second step classifies and refines these proposals.

4) *Accuracy*:: Faster R-CNN is noted for its accuracy and is appropriate for tasks requiring precision, such fine-grained object recognition or medical imaging. Complexity: Faster R-CNN is more computationally intensive than YOLO, although being as accurate, which may influence its real-time performance on devices with limited resources.

Fig. 4. Traditional neural network vs CNN

C. Image Processing Techniques:

Image preprocessing algorithms may be utilized to enhance the quality of input images, such as noise reduction, image resizing, histogram equalization, or normalization. Feature extraction methods might also be applied to extract relevant features from face images, such as facial landmarks or descriptors like Eigenfaces or Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG).

D. Attendance Management Algorithm:

An algorithm for managing attendance records could involve techniques like database management, data storage, and retrieval. It might include operations like adding new entries, marking attendance for recognized faces, generating reports, etc.

E. Machine Learning Algorithms:

Machine learning algorithms could be employed for various purposes such as: Classifying faces into different categories (e.g., students, teachers, staff). Predicting attendance trends based on historical data. Identifying anomalies or irregular attendance patterns.

F. Data Processing and Analysis:

Algorithms for data processing and analysis could include statistical methods, clustering algorithms, or time-series analysis techniques to derive insights from attendance data.

G. Real-time Monitoring and Alerts:

Algorithms for real-time monitoring may involve techniques for continuous video processing, event detection, and triggering alerts or notifications based on predefined rules or thresholds.

H. User Interface and Interaction:

Algorithms for user interface design and interaction could involve human-computer interaction principles, graphical user interface (GUI) design, and algorithms for handling user inputs and feedback.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Data Collection

Our dataset is a collection of 100 images that were collected using an front-facing web-camera which is a 5-megapixel, f/2.2 lens. The data was classified into 10 classes, each individual class includes 20 images.

B. Data Formatting

The collected data is used in a JPG file formatting. The image sizes are ranging between 1.00 MB and 2.00 MB. Each net has different input size. Therefore, we had to resize the images to the corresponding input dimensions of the network. SqueezeNet and AlexNet uses 227×227 , while GoogleNet uses 224×224 . All the images taken are in RGB colors which is good to extract the right features.

C. Data Augmentation

Data augmentation is a tool used to increase the amount of data by inserting slightly changed copies of existing data or newly produced synthetic data from existing data. It regularizes and helps in the training of a machine learning model to minimize overfitting. In deep learning, data augmentation comes in a form of geometric transformations, flipping, color alteration, cropping, rotation, noise injection and random erasing are used to enhance the image [8]. In our trained networks, we used data augmentation by taking multiple images from different angles, environments and conditions, orientation, location, and brightness as shown in Fig. 5. After importing our data to the network, we applied two types of data augmentation which are rotation and scaling. A random rotation is performed on each image by an angle in the range of -90 to 90 degrees. A random scaling is performed on each image by a factor in the range of 1 to 2.

D. Choice of pre-trained networks

To train the convolution neural network on our data, we chose 3 nets to work with which are, SqueezeNet, AlexNet, and GoogleNet. SqueezeNet is small CNN and need less communication between servers during distributed training. Smaller CNNs are also easier to implement on hardware with limited memory, such as a fieldprogrammable gate array (FPGA). AlexNet can easily pass learned features to a special

assignment with a smaller number of training images. AlexNet was developed to enhance the performance of the ImageNet challenge. This was one of the first Deep convolutional networks to reach significant accuracy. The overfitting problem is also solved by AlexNet by using drop-out layers where a connection is dropped with a probability of $p=0.5$ during testing. A probability of 0.5 was chosen because it was the best probability to match the net specifications and training options. This was set after many trials and changes. Although this prevents the overfitting of the network by having it escape from bad local minima, the number of iterations needed for convergence has also doubled. The inception module in the GoogleNet architecture solved most of the challenges that large networks had. GoogleNet is scoring a 6.67pc error rate which is close to human level performance. The architecture consisted of 22 layers of the Deep CNN reducing the number of parameters to 4 million (60 million compared from AlexNet).

E. Training

The generic procedure when training any network using transfer learning starts with modifying the parameters belonging to the base architecture. This includes choosing an appropriate learning rate, training time, number of epochs, and the validation frequency. When the initial rate is too low, the training process may become stalled, and when the rate is too high, the training process may become unstable or learn a sub-optimal set of weights too quickly. Therefore, we chose the initial learning rate to be set to 0.0001, the validation frequency is 10, and maximum epochs are 30 because it should be as high as possible to eliminate the failure of training pauses based on the error rates. To be specific, an epoch is a single learning cycle during which the learner is exposed to the whole training data set. Also, the minimum batch size is equal to 11, this fits the memory requirements (8.00 GB) of the CPU hardware that is operating using 1.8 GHz. The higher the number of epochs, the higher the accuracy of the network. Therefore, we had to choose a bigger number. The data set was randomly split into two parts: 70 percent of the data is used for training and 30 percent of the data is used for validation.

F. Attendance Marking

For each face detected and matched with enrolled face, the attendance is marked for the corresponding USN in the database. The name of student along with day and time of attendance is also be stored in the database.

VII. RESULTS

Smart-Attendance-Management-System is a very easy to use tool and it functions very efficiently as the results of the experiments suggests using deep algorithms in our attendance system makes it drastically accurate since the accuracy of this algorithm from different angles is 95 percent [15] and the maximum distance of 7 feet can be recognized with

94 percent accuracy which makes it a beneficial and useful method. The system works automatically after every student is been registered by the teacher and the dataset is created. The frontend or the GUI of our project is consisting of the following main three parts:

- Registration
- Face Recognition
- Adding the name and time
- Attendance sheet generation and exporting it to web-page

Fig. 5. Home Page

	A	B	C	D
1	Name	Roll	Time	
2	Aman	2	21:32:43	
3	Abhishek	1	21:32:43	
4	Sumit	3	21:32:43	
5				
6				

Fig. 6. Attendance Sheet

For the initialization phase the teacher need to enter the student (“name”, “roll number”, “course”). along with 200 photos of each student from different angles as a dataset for training purpose. This Attendance-system is able to recognize images from different angles and different light conditions. Those students whose faces are not in the data set will be marked as unknown [17].

The “attendance” of the recognized students is marked in the meantime. And exported to the excel sheet and will be saved by the system automatically after using Viola-Jones for face detection and deep learning techniques to calculate and compare 128-d face features for face recognition as the results of the experiments shows we have made the attendance system drastically accurate.

Since it can recognize the face from different angles 95 percent accurately and the maximum distance of 7 feet can be recognized with 94 percent accuracy which makes it a beneficial and useful method.

The main motive of this project is to make the attendance system completely automatic and more accurate so that the

issues with the currently available attendance systems do not bother the faculties and students of our institution which we have achieved by using these two algorithms (Histogram of Oriented Gradient and deep learning

techniques) to reduce the chances of any error and failure. This system will require maintenance work which will also enhance the performance in future.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTION

In conclusion, the Smart Attendance using Face Recognition system offers a sophisticated yet practical solution for attendance monitoring in diverse settings such as educational institutions, workplaces, and events. By leveraging advanced face recognition technology, the system streamlines the attendance tracking process, promoting accuracy, reliability, and convenience.

The successful implementation of this project signifies its potential to revolutionize traditional attendance systems and contribute to the advancement of automated monitoring systems. Moving forward, further enhancements and optimizations can be explored to enhance the system’s performance and functionality, catering to evolving needs and requirements.

Overall, the Smart Attendance using Face Recognition system represents a significant advancement in attendance management technology, with promising implications for enhancing productivity, security, and user experience across various sectors.

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